

Waveform Performance in 5G Air Interface: A Comprehensive Review of Multicarrier Modulation Schemes

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Abstract.

With the growing demand for high-quality, low-latency video and multimedia applications on wireless devices, today's cellular providers are seeking advanced solutions. This has led to the emergence of fifth-generation (5G) mobile communication systems. One of the most widely adopted multicarrier modulation techniques is Cyclic Prefix-Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (CP-OFDM). However, CP-OFDM suffers from poor out-of-band (OoB) radiation due to the use of rectangular pulse shaping filters, and the cyclic prefix reduces spectral efficiency. These limitations make CP-OFDM less suitable for future wireless networks.

To address these challenges, Filter Bank Multicarrier with Offset Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (FBMC-OQAM) has gained increasing attention as a promising alternative. The objective of this study is to analyze the applicability of FBMC-OQAM for next-generation communication systems. A comprehensive comparison between OFDM and FBMC is conducted based on key performance metrics, including spectral efficiency, power spectral density (PSD), and ambiguity diagrams.

Simulation results demonstrate that FBMC offers superior bandwidth efficiency compared to OFDM, indicating its potential to support the demands of future wireless networks such as 5G.

Keywords: OFDM, FBMC, PSD, OQAM, OoB

1 Introduction

Multicarrier (MC) modulations have been the major physical layer transmission technology adopted in Long Term Evolution (LTE). MC modulation's basic concept is to divide the digital bitstream to be transmitted via a wideband channel into a lower rate collection of parallel bitstreams. Each of these bitstreams is transmitted so that the entire channel is transmitted using a different frequency sub band. The primary advantage of this wideband channel conversion into a series of parallel flat fading narrowband channels is that this dramatically decreases the receiver's difficulty in

terms of equalization and also channel estimation. OFDM is a multicarrier system in which all sub-carriers are orthogonal to each other, resulting in no interference. Overall, OFDM is one of the most advanced modulation methods used in mobile 4 G communication, like the LTE (Long Term Evolution) framework.

As today's society relies more and more on wireless connections, To improve their lives, there is a very high demand for capacity for the transmission of large quantities of data, and lower latencies are required at the same time. The existing 4 G networks will not solve these concerns due to their inherent OFDM architecture limitations. FBMC is an OFDM multicarrier advanced technique where a set of filters is used at the transmitter and receiver instead of CP[1], which nullifies ISI's impact without the use of CP, OFDM making it effective compared to OFDM in terms of bandwidth efficiency. Because of their less Out of Band (OoB) radiation, Concerning OFDM, the key difference between FBMC and OFDM [2] is that a more sophisticated prototype filter is used instead of rectangular windows. It uses a filter that can reduce the leakage of out-of-band radiation and help to satisfy improved spectral efficiency. The use of FBMC with suitable prototypes filter enables almost zero inter-symbol interference (ISI) to be achieved. This article is structured as follows. We are explaining the OFDM System in Sec. 2. The proposed FBMC system is listed in Section 3. Performance metric of Multicarrier modulation schemes, and; 9i Simulation outcomes are discussed in Sec. 4. In Sec. 5, the conclusions are drawn.

2 OFDM System

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) is a digital multicarrier modulation method that, through the use of multiple subcarriers within the same single-channel, extends the principle of single subcarrier modulation. OFDM [3] makes use of a large number of closely-spaced orthogonal subcarriers that are transmitted in parallel, rather than transmitting a high-rate data stream with a single subcarrier. With a traditional digital modulation scheme at a low symbol rate, each subcarrier is modulated. However, several subcarriers' combination makes data rates within the corresponding bandwidths close to traditional single-carrier modulation schemes.

OFDM is based on the well-known Frequency Division Multiplexing (FDM) technique. Various information sources are mapped to different parallel frequency channels in the FDM. To minimize interference between adjacent channels, each FDM channel is separated from the others by a frequency guard band.

The input bits are grouped and mapped to source data symbols in a digitally implemented OFDM system that is a complex number reflecting the modulation constellation point (e.g., the BPSK or QAM symbols that would be present in a single subcarrier system). The transmitter handles these complex source symbols as if they are in the frequency-domain and are the inputs to an IFFT block that translates the data into the time-domain. At a time when N is the number of subcarriers in the system, the IFFT absorbs N source symbols. There is a symbol time of T seconds in

each of these N input symbols. Recall that N orthogonal sinusoids are the output of the IFFT. They also have a different frequency of these orthogonal sinusoids, and DC is the lowest frequency. Therefore, a simple way to modulate data on N orthogonal subcarriers is given by the IFFT block. A single OFDM symbol makes up the block of N output samples from the IFFT.

The time-domain signal that emerges from the IFFT is transmitted through the radio channel after some extra processing. An FFT block is used on the receiver to process the received signal and carry it into the frequency domain that is used to recover the original bits of data. The use of orthogonal subcarriers makes it possible to improve the spectral efficiency of more subcarriers per Bandwidth. Orthogonality eliminates interference between overlapping carriers in a perfect OFDM signal. Any overlap in the spectrums of neighboring signals in FDM systems can result in interference. In OFDM systems, only when there is a lack of orthogonality can the subcarriers conflict with each other.

In an OFDM transmitter, using a serial-to-parallel-converter, input bits are first grouped into symbols in the frequency domain. The IFFT then takes these frequency domain symbols as its input. By performing an IFFT operation on the input, the IFFT block transforms the input symbol into the time domain symbol. The cyclic prefix is applied via the cyclic prefix block to the output of the IFFT block. The parallel-to-serial converter then transforms this symbol back to a sequence of bits and transmits it. The input signal is passed through the channel equalizer block in the OFDM receiver first to eliminate any impairment caused by the wireless channel. To remove the cyclic prefix, the output of the equalizer is then entered into the prefix extraction block. The FFT block is then given the output of the prefix extraction block. By doing an FFT operation, this block converts the input to frequency domain output. The OFDM receiver thus recovers the original bits via a parallel-to-serial operation.

3 FBMC/OQAM System

The filter bank multicarrier (FBMC)[4][11-13] is an enabling technology for new concepts. The combination of filter banks with OQAM modulation, without the need for a guard time or cyclic prefix as in OFDM, leads to the maximum bit rate. Concerning implementation, the filter bank approach is only an extension of the direct FFT approach and with an extended FFT, the so-called polyphase network (PPN)-FFT technique, that needs fewer computations.

The Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) can act as a multicarrier modulator, while the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) can act as a multicarrier

demodulator. The data block in the transmitter at the IFFT input is recovered in the receiver at the output of the FFT since the FFT and IFFT are cascaded. In the FBMC system, only odd or even indexed subchannels are used. However, all sub-channels must be utilized if maximum speed is desired, and a particular modulation is needed to cope with the frequency domain overlap of the neighboring sub-channels. The technique for achieving maximum capacity is as follows: double the symbol rate and use the real and the imaginary portion of the IFFT alternatively for each sub-channel. Therefore, the real and imaginary part of a complex data symbol is not simultaneously transmitted as in OFDM, but half the symbol duration delays the imaginary part. This process is the so-called modulation of the offset quadrature amplitude (OQAM). The term 'offset' represents the time change between the real part and the imaginary part of a complex symbol of half the inverse of the sub-channel spacing. With the use of generic prototype filters on multicarrier systems and due to the additional filtering activities at the transmitter and the receiver, high complexity can be added. The use of polyphase representations[4] of filters and FFT operations will reduce this complexity. Filter Length is considered as KM.

4 Performance Metric

4.1 Spectral Efficiency

In a particular communication system, spectral efficiency or Bandwidth efficiency refers to the information rate that can be transmitted over a specified bandwidth. It can be defined as the efficient and useful use of all the frequencies Hertz available for communication. Bandwidth efficiency is important in radio communication as the available Bandwidth is very small for communication. So bandwidth efficiency can be improved (by increasing the number of bits per Hertz). We want to help a greater number of devices per unit region in 5G. We know that the number of traffic-generating devices will continue to grow. It is increasingly popular for each user to continuously upgrade augmented reality glasses, smartphones, tablets, laptops, and probably other devices and update their status and data transmission through the wireless communication link. Therefore, it is necessary to enhance the spectral efficiency performance of the system.

The spectral efficiency of the waveform modulation technique of OFDM and FBMC[5] is given by the

Where m is the numb

$$\eta_{OFDM} = \frac{m \times N_{FFT}}{N_{FFT} + N_{CP}}$$

(1)

$$\eta_{FBMC} = \frac{m \times S}{S + K - \frac{1}{2}} \tag{2}$$

Where m is the number of bits per subcarrier, N_{FFT} is FFT Size, N_{CP} is cyclic prefix length, K is the overlapping factor of the filter, and S is the number of symbols in a burst.

Fig.1. shows OFDM and FBMC's bandwidth efficiency with FFT point 512, bits per subcarrier is equal to 6, and the overlapping factor is equal to 4, and the burst duration is up to 500 ms. OFDM spectral efficiency is constant during the burst duration where FBMC Spectral Efficiency(SE) increases rapidly with burst duration up to 80 ms, after around 80 ms spectral efficiency of FBMC increases gradually. For long burst duration, the spectral efficiency of FBMC is better.

Fig. 1. Spectral Efficiency Comparison

The spectral effectiveness of FBMC can be increased by increasing the bits per subcarrier or by decreasing the overlapping factor and by increasing the burst length. As our result shows, OFDM has a low spectral efficiency compared to FBMC. This effect is due to the OFDM wide frequency guard and CP. Unlike OFDM, Cyclic Prefix is not used by FBMC, which increases spectral effectiveness.

Table 1. SE Comparison for OFDM &FBMC System

No. of Bits Per Subcarrier(m)	2	4	6	8
SE-OFDM(b/s/Hz)	1.6	3.2	4.8	6.4
SE-FBMC(b/s/Hz)	1.966	3.931	5.897	7.862

Table 1. shows the Spectral efficiency of OFDM and FBMC for different m values for FFT size 512 and overlapping factor K=4 under the burst size 200ms. It has been observed from the table, an increase in m increases the spectral efficiency. For m=4, the spectral efficiency is measured as 3.2b/s/Hz for the OFDM system, and for the FBMC system, it is measured as 3.931 b/s/Hz. In the FBMC system, spectral efficiency is 22% improved compared to that of the OFDM system.

Fig. 2. shows the spectral efficiency of the FBMC system for different overlapping factors; from the figure, it has been observed that for a smaller value of K, spectral efficiency is improved. It is noted from the table, for K=2, spectral efficiency is 3.721 b/s/Hz, whereas, for K=8, Spectral efficiency is 2.909 b/s/Hz.

Fig. 2. SE Comparison of different K

Table 2. SE Comparison for FBMC System for Different K

Overlapping Factor (K)	2	4	6	8
SE-FBMC(b/s/Hz) measured at 20 ms	3.721	3.4	3.13	2.909
SE-FBMC(b/s/Hz) measured at 80 ms	3.926	3.832	3.743	3.657

Table 2 shows the Spectral efficiency for the FBMC system by taking values of NFFT=512,m=4, varying K, value SE is measured under burst duration 20, and 80ms. From the table, it is noted that for longer burst sizes, the spectral efficiency is improved. For burst size 20ms and K=2, the spectral efficiency is 3.721 b/s/Hz, whereas, for 80 ms burst size, the spectral efficiency is 3.926 b/s/Hz

4.2 Power Spectral Density

FBMC's Power Spectral Density(PSD) occupies its Bandwidth within the frequency range of -0.3 and $+0.3$. But outside this range, the PSD is not allowed because it is considered to be out of band emission and leads to interference with the symbol (ISI). In terms of PSD, FBMC shows lower OOB[2] than OFDM and can be implemented for longer burst length; FBMC is preferable to reduce the ISI and ICI that is the prerequisite for 5 G devices.

Fig. 3. PSD of FBMC for Different K

Fig. 3. shows the FBMC system's PSD for various overlapping factors, Bandwidth occupied for $K=3$ and $K=4$ are the same, but out of band leakage for $K=3$ is high compared to $K=4$. Useful bandwidth for $K=2$ is -0.1 and $+0.1$. beyond this range will lead to ISI.

4.3 Ambiguity Diagram

The ambiguity function[6] is a two-dimensional autocorrelation in the time and frequency plane, which is the correlation between the filter coefficients and its frequency-modulated versions. The plot of the ambiguity surface is called the ambiguity diagram. Ambiguity function in terms of Nyquist Criteria is given by

$$A(p\tau_0, kv_0) = \{1, p = k = 0, \text{ otherwise}\}$$

(3)

The ambiguity surface[7] describes the side-lobe levels of the combined transmit-receive filter response in time and frequency domains, respectively. The two main properties of the Ambiguity function[7] are that the peak value of the ambiguity

surface is one, and it is obtained in origin (0,0). The second property of the Ambiguity function follows symmetric in both the vertical and horizontal axis.

Fig. 4. Ambiguity diagram of Rectangular Filter

Fig. 5. Ambiguity diagram of PHYDYAS Filter

The contour plot of the ambiguity function of the PHYDYAS filter is shown in Fig. 5. The mapping between the magnitude values and the color can be obtained from the color bar beside the contour plots. The maximum amount occurs at the center, and a value becomes low as it moves from the center. The ambiguity function values at normalized symbol and subcarrier spacing points with central element $A(0,0)$ is 1.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, Filter Bank Multicarrier (FBMC), particularly with Offset Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (FBMC-OQAM), presents itself as a strong contender for next-generation wireless communication systems. It effectively addresses several drawbacks of traditional OFDM, offering superior spectral efficiency and improved power spectral density (PSD). Simulation results consistently highlight FBMC's ability to reduce out-of-band emissions and enhance spectral containment, which are critical for high-capacity, interference-sensitive environments. Given its advantages such as the elimination of the cyclic prefix, better time-frequency localization, and efficient spectrum usage, FBMC is well-suited for advanced applications in mobile broadband and the Internet of Things (IoT). Overall, FBMC-OQAM stands out as a promising solution to meet the stringent demands of future wireless networks, positioning itself as a viable alternative to OFDM for 5G, 6G, and beyond.

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